

Extended Data pertaining to the manuscript:

Representations of Economic Inequality and Welfare Redistribution in British Mainstream Party Programs, 2005–2024, by Daniel Walsh and Sonja Zmerli

Table 1: Table of British Main Party Manifesto Text Lengths in words 2005 - 2024

Year	Conservative	Labour	Liberal Democrats	Scottish National Party	Year Average
2005	6,858	27,929	16,317	12,272	15,844
2010	28,018	29,676	19,940	8,583	21,554
2015	30,811	18,466	35,115	18,776	25,792
2017	30,217	24,161	21,355	20,397	24,032
2019	20,950	25,876	27,541	21,693	24,015
2024	26,324	26,040	22,141	8,120	20,656
Party Average	23,863	25,358	23,734	14,973	

Figure 1: Graph of British Main Party Manifesto Text Lengths in words 2005 - 2024

Table 2: Top-10 Words associated with Inequality and Equality in British Party Manifesto 2005 - 2024

Inequality only	Equality only	Inequality or Equality
equality	inequality	poverty
poverty	poverty	opportunity
government	opportunity	sex
people	sex	people
progressive	people	government
reduce	government	country
social	country	tackling
problems	tackling	work
better	work	marriage
family	marriage	children

Economic Inequality Keywords:

Keywords derived from: McGovern, Patrick, Bauer, Martin and Obradovic, Sandra (2023). In search of a Tawney Moment: Income inequality, financial crisis and the mass media in the UK and the USA. *The Sociological Review*, 71(5): 1213–1233.

Category: Economic:

Wealth
Income
Economy
Salary
Compensation
Pay

Category: Inequality

Inequality
Equality
Distribution
Differential

Redistribution Keywords:

Attendance Allowance
Additional State Pension
Armed Forces Compensation Scheme
Bereavement Allowance
Bereavement Payment
Bereavement Support Payment
Budgeting Loan
Benefit Cap
Benefit Support for Housing Costs
Carer's Allowance
Carer's Credit
Child Benefit
Child Funeral Fund
Child Maintenance
Child Tax Credits
Christmas Bonus
Cold Weather Payment
Constant Attendance Allowance
Crisis Loans
Cost of Living Payments
Childcare Support for Students
Carer's Leave
Council Tax Reduction Schemes
Coronavirus Job Retention Scheme
Citizens' Rights Provisions
Disability Living Allowance
Disability Benefit Assessments
Discretionary Housing Payments
Domestic Abuse Support
DWP Benefit Sanctions
Employment and Support Allowance
ESA
Early Intervention Policies
Finance Support
Funeral Expenses Payment
Free School Meals Support
Furlough Scheme
Guardians Allowance
Help with Health Costs
Home Responsibilities Protection
Housing Benefit
Housing Benefit Extended Payment
Healthy Start Scheme
High Income Child Benefit Charge
Help with Childcare Costs

Help with Energy Bills
Household Support Fund
Income Support
Independent Living Fund
Industrial Injuries Disablement Benefit
Jobseeker's Allowance
JSA
Local Housing Allowance
LHA
Maternity Allowance
Motability
National Insurance Number
No Recourse to Public Funds
Over 80 Pension
Pension Credit
Personal Independence Payment
PIP
Reduced Earnings Allowance
Redundancy Pay
Rent Safety Net
Severe Disablement Allowance
State Pension
Statutory Adoption Pay
Statutory Maternity Pay
Statutory Paternity Pay
Statutory Sick Pay
SSP
Sure Start Maternity Grant
Support for Mortgage Interest
SMI
Support for Single Parent Families
Social Security
Supported Exempt Accommodation
Tax Credits
Test and Trace Support Payments
Triple-Lock
Universal Credit
Universal Basic Income
Universal Credit Uplift
Universal Credit Assessment Period and Earned Income
War Disablement Pension
War Widow or Widower's Pension
Widowed Parent's Allowance
Winter Fuel Payment
Working Tax Credit
Work Capability Assessment

Table 3: Economic Inequality Semantic Frequency

Year	Conservative	Labour	LibDem	SNP
2005	3	5	7	4
2010	13	6	5	0
2015	6	5	15	16
2017	10	19	10	11
2019	1	24	16	9
2024	3	6	8	2

Table 4: Economic Inequality Semantic Frequency Normalised by Manifesto Length *100

Year	Conservative	Labour	LibDem	SNP
2005	0.0437	0.0179	0.0429	0.0326
2010	0.0464	0.0202	0.0251	0.0
2015	0.0195	0.0271	0.0427	0.0852
2017	0.0331	0.0786	0.0468	0.0539
2019	0.0048	0.0928	0.0581	0.0415
2024	0.0114	0.023	0.0361	0.0476

Table 5: Redistribution Semantic Frequency

Year	Conservative	Labour	LibDem	SNP
2005	11	13	9	5
2010	12	25	22	5
2015	27	20	32	33
2017	24	26	22	49
2019	12	30	14	46
2024	22	10	23	3

Table 6: Redistribution Semantic Frequency Normalised by Manifesto Length *100

Year	Conservative	Labour	LibDem	SNP
2005	0.01604	0.0465	0.0552	0.0407
2010	0.0428	0.0842	0.1103	0.0583
2015	0.0876	0.1083	0.0911	0.1758
2017	0.0794	0.1076	0.103	0.2402
2019	0.0573	0.1159	0.0508	0.212
2024	0.0836	0.0384	0.1039	0.0369

Table 7: Year-by-year changes in Gini coefficients (to two decimal points) for the financial years ending 2005–2022 are derived from UK Gini coefficient data for 1977–2022, as produced by the Office for National Statistics (Clark, 2024).

Year	GINI	Year-on-Year Change (%)
2004/05	34.3	
2005/06	35.9	1.6
2006/07	37.0	1.1
2007/08	38.6	1.6
2008/09	35.6	-3.0
2009/10	36.6	1.0
2010/11	34.1	-2.5
2011/12	33.8	-0.3
2012/13	34.4	0.6
2013/14	35.3	0.9
2014/15	34.7	-0.6
2015/16	35.1	0.4
2016/17	33.4	-1.7
2017/18	35.0	1.6
2018/19	36.0	1.0
2019/20	35.4	-0.6
2020/21	34.4	-1.0
2021/22	35.7	1.3